

Innovative Bioelectrochemical Approach to Textile Wastewater Treatment: Harnessing MFCs for Energy Recovery and Dye Decolorization

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Abstract

The development of eco-friendly technologies for treating dye-contaminated wastewater is both an urgent necessity for reducing water resource pollution and a significant challenge due to the toxic and persistent nature of most dyes. In this context, the present study examined the influence of Indigo Carmine (IC), a model dye widely used in the textile industry, on decolorization, chemical oxygen demand (COD) removal, and bioelectricity generation through bioelectrochemical technology using a Microbial Fuel Cell (MFC) inoculated with anaerobic sludge. The results revealed that MFC-mediated biodecolorization of IC dye exhibited 34.20% efficiency, with COD removal reaching 185.07 mg L⁻¹ (33.68%) and remarkable bioenergy production, attaining peak values of 200.31 mA m⁻² and 31.25 mW m⁻² for current and power density, respectively. These findings highlight the potential for advancing MFC technology as a promising and innovative step towards sustainability, enabling the use of renewable resources to generate clean energy while simultaneously remediating environmentally hazardous effluents.

Keywords

Bioelectrochemical technology; bioenergy generation; Microbial Fuel Cell; Indigo Carmine; textile dyes; decolorization

INTRODUCTION

In the last few years, significant research efforts have been dedicated to enhancing Microbial Fuel Cells (MFCs) due to their potential to generate energy in an environmentally friendly manner. MFCs function as bioreactors capable of directly transforming the chemical energy stored in the bonds of organic and inorganic compounds into electricity (Logan & Regan, 2006). One of the most promising applications of MFCs lies in wastewater treatment, where pollutants serve as substrates for electroactive microorganisms, enabling the integration of bioremediation processes with bioenergy production (Kardi et al., 2017; Rathour et al., 2019). Among these, dye-contaminated wastewater has shown a particularly high potential for remediation using MFC technology.

The textile industry is recognized as one of the leading contributors to water pollution, releasing vast quantities of hazardous effluents into the environment annually (N Lotha et al., 2024). Approximately 20% of global water pollution is attributed to textile sector activities, making it the second-largest water-polluting industry after petrochemicals (Periyasamy, 2024; UNEP, 2018). The chemical stability, high solubility and low biodegradability of the dyes present in textile wastewater make it one of the most complex and difficult industrial effluents to treat. Thus, conventional physicochemical methods are becoming outdated due to various limitations, including their low efficiency and versatility, sludge generation and secondary pollutants produced (Srivastava et al., 2022; Tacas et al., 2021).

In this context, MFCs present several advantages over traditional wastewater treatment methods, combining biological and electrochemical processes, delivering enhanced treatment efficiency, producing minimal sludge, and functioning as self-sustaining systems (Rathour et al., 2019). This study investigated the treatment of dye-contaminated synthetic solutions using a single-chamber MFC populated with anaerobic sludge. The remediation of the model dye Indigo Carmine (IC) was evaluated with regard to the effect of different initial dye concentrations on color removal efficiency, chemical oxygen demand (COD) reduction and bioenergy generation.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Textile dyes

Indigo carmine (IC), also known as Acid Blue 74 (CI. 73015) (Neon Comercial, Brazil) was used as the representative textile dye in this study. The synthetic solutions were prepared in the required concentrations by diluting the stock solution (1.0 g L^{-1}) in distilled water.

MFC setup and operation

The single-chamber microbial fuel cell (MFC) with air-cathode was constructed from acrylic material, featuring a prismatic design with a square base ($13.0 \text{ cm} \times 13.0 \text{ cm}$) and a total capacity of 1 L. The electrode comprised a carbon paper anode and a carbon cloth cathode coated with a microporous layer of carbon nanoparticles and PTFE polymer, separated by a Nafion™ 212 proton exchange membrane (Novocell, Americana-Brazil). The cathode, with a nominal area of 141.6 cm^2 , had a catalyst load of $0.4 \text{ mg Pt cm}^{-2}$. A digital multimeter with a datalogger was employed to monitor voltage and record data at 1-minute intervals, and an external resistor of $1000 \ \Omega$ was connected to the system.

Anaerobic sludge from a municipal wastewater treatment plant was used as inoculum. The synthetic solution consisted of phosphate buffer solution (PBS), enriched with nutrients, acetate (0.5 g L^{-1}) and dye at the required concentration (100 or 500 mg L^{-1} of IC). The MFC was operated in fed-batch mode with a hydraulic retention time (HRT) of 24 hours.

Performance assessment

The performance of the MFC was evaluated in terms of IC removal, COD reduction and bioelectricity generation. The decolorization of the samples was determined in a UV-Vis spectrophotometer (HACH DR/3900) at λ 610 nm, after centrifugation. The closed reflux method using the HACH kit (APHA, 2012) was used to measure COD. And the polarization tests were used to determine the maximum current and power densities, which were obtained by operating the MFC in open circuit for around 30 minutes and then the external resistances were varied between 1000 and $10 \ \Omega$ at 10-minute intervals, with the current generation being monitored after reaching stabilization.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results of MFC performance after acclimatization and biofilm formation in the treatment of IC dye are shown in **Table 1**.

Table 1. Quantification and COD and color removal efficiency of IC dye.

C_0 dye (mg L^{-1})	Removed dye (mg L^{-1})	Dye removal (%)	Removed COD (mg L^{-1})	COD removal (%)
100	34.20 ± 0.17	34.20 ± 0.17	185.07 ± 4.73	33.68 ± 0.86
500	119.00 ± 12.5	23.80 ± 2.50	126.48 ± 0.70	21.77 ± 0.12

It was found that the best removal performance of 34.20% (34.20 mg L^{-1}) was achieved with the

application of the lowest initial dye concentration (100 mg L^{-1}). Despite the increase in the amount of dye removed (119.00 mg L^{-1}), the removal percentage decreased to 23.80% when increasing the initial IC concentration to 500 mg L^{-1} . The concentration of dyes plays a critical role in the decolorization process, as high concentrations can exhibit toxic effects on microorganisms (Singh, 2015). Solanki et al. (Solanki et al., 2013) observed that the behavior exhibited by the IC dye is the most typical; generally, decolorization efficiency declines as dye concentration rises. This phenomenon is attributed to co-substrate limitations, leading to an electron deficit at the anode, which hinders the effective reduction of dye molecules at higher concentrations (Tan et al., 2021). With regard to organic matter, the best COD removal, around 34% (185.07 mg L^{-1}), was also obtained for the lowest IC concentration. Both the removal efficiency and the absolute COD reduction (in mg L^{-1}) decreased as the dye concentration increased. As reported by Sun et al. (Sun et al., 2009), the reduction in COD removal efficiency at higher dye concentrations can be attributed to the accumulation of intermediate compounds generated during dye degradation, further increasing the COD content in the anodic medium.

The bioelectricity generation performance of the MFC (Figure 1), in turn, showed the opposite behavior to the IC decolorization. Maximum output voltages of 296 and 300 mV, current densities of 200.31 and 210.58 mA m^{-2} and power densities of 31.25 and 34.54 mW m^{-2} were obtained at 100 and 500 mg L^{-1} , respectively. Similar values have been reported by other authors in similar systems treating different dyes, for which maximum power densities of 7.07 to 39.98 mW m^{-2} were achieved (Tan et al., 2021; Thung et al., 2015). Oon et al. (Oon et al., 2017) state that the power density produced is strongly associated with the chemical structure of the dyes. The presence of sulfonic groups, which are strong electron withdrawing groups, as well as the high redox potential of IC favor its electrochemical reduction, allowing greater electron transfer to the anode at higher dye concentrations (Çekiç et al., 2010; Logan, 2008).

Figure 1. (a) Polarization and (b) power density curves of the MFC at different IC dye concentrations.

CONCLUSION

The findings of this study showed a better decolorization and COD removal performance for lower initial dye concentrations, whereas the highest concentration favored bioenergy generation. At elevated dye levels, electrochemical oxidation was enhanced, facilitating greater electron transfer to the anode and boosting bioelectricity production in the MFC.

Advancing this innovative and eco-friendly technology marks a significant step toward a circular economy and sustainable development. It offers an alternative source of clean, renewable electricity while simultaneously mitigating environmental pollution by eliminating highly contaminating dyes.

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